

Assessment of Pollution Status of Pushkar Lake in two Different occasions by Using Water Quality Index

Paper Id : 19092 Submission Date : 2024-05-09 Acceptance Date : 2024-05-22 Publication Date : 2024-05-25

This is an open-access research paper/article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

DOI:10.5281/zenodo.13148580

For verification of this paper, please visit on <http://www.socialresearchfoundation.com/researchtimes.php#8>

Rakesh Kumar Baser

Assistant Professor
Dept. Of Zoology
Samrat Prithviraj Chauhan
Government College
Ajmer, Rajasthan, India

Abstract

Water bodies are one of the world's most productive systems. They provide a variety of commodities and services for the benefit of humans, as well as recreational, aesthetic, and cultural value. The research was conducted in 2019-2020 during the Makar Sankranti and Vaishakh Snan festivals at Pushkar Lake. The aimed study assesses the water quality of Pushkar Lake of Ajmer applying National Sanitation Foundation (NSF) America developed index called Water Quality Index (WQI). Total 8 physicochemical parameters were measured to calculate the index. The observed value of Water quality index reflected that lake belongs to "C" category of CPCB on 100-point scale with average water quality. This low value was related to human activities in the region during the festivals. The implementation of WQI is necessary for public and decision makers to evaluate the water quality of the lakes for sustainable management. On the basis of physiochemical analysis, it has been concluded that strict practices have been needed to stop anthropogenic activities to prevent Pushkar lake from huge pollution.

Keywords Pushkar, Pollution, Makar Sankranti, Vaishakh Snan, Water Quality Index.

Introduction Water is one of the essential components for the survival of life on Earth and one of the most precious natural resources whose quality is critical to human existence. The total accessible water on Earth has been estimated is 1.4 billion cubic kilometers, forming a layer of about 3 km depth. About 97.5% (Shiklomanov, 1993) of the Earth's water is useless for human consumption due to high salt content. From the available 2.5% of fresh water, nearly 68.6% is in ice caps, glaciers and undying snow. The remaining unfrozen fresh water is groundwater (30.1%) and surface water (1.3%). Only 20.56% of the available surface water found in Lakes is suitable for human consumption. This highlights how precious the freshwater possessions are. Both ground and surface water can be used by humans. The world's freshwater ecosystems encompass only about 0.5% of the Earth's surface and have a volume of $2.84 \times 10^5 \text{ km}^3$ (Wetzel, 2001). Water quality is described according to its physical, chemical, and biological parameters. In recent years, the increasing personal influences in and around our aquatic systems and their catchments areas have led to the decline of water quality and eutrophication (Bhatt *et al.*, 1999). Water is an important issue to be investigated in water resources management. As there is lack of consensus among different experts and end users regarding perceptions and interpretation of various parameters of water quality. Therefore, it is necessary to translate water quality data in widely acceptable and unambiguous term. One of the most effective approaches for studying water quality is using of suitable indices which provide single value to the water quality in order to reach comprehensive, dynamic and consistent picture of pollution load of water body. (Prati 1971, Brown *et al.*, 1970, Sanchez *et al.*, 2007)

In general water quality indices, data from numerous water quality parameters is incorporated into mathematical equation that rates the healthiness of water body with a single number, which is placed on a relative scale to validate the water quality in category ranging from very bad to excellent for consumers unambiguousness. A number of indices have been developed to summarize water quality data for communication to the general public in an effective way. A commonly widely used WQI was developed by the National Sanitation Foundation (NSF) in 1970 (Brown *et al.*, 1970). Essentially, the NSF WQI

converts the concentration data for eight analytes into one of five water quality classes, ranging from very bad" to excellent. Present study is carried out to achieve water quality status of Pushkar lake by using Water Quality Index.

Objective of study The main objective of study is to access the water quality status of Pushkar lake by using NSFQI.

Review of Literature Manderia *et al.*, (2014) assessed the water quality of Anchar Lake, Kashmir and found nutrient enrichment of the lake due to anthropogenic pressure, siltation and the effluent released from Sheri-Kashmir Institute of Medical Sciences (SKIMS). Shekar *et al.*, (2015) evaluated the water quality status of Gidadakonenhalli Lake in Bangalore city, Karnataka using Water Quality Index (WQI) and found significant seasonal variation in the water quality of the Lake with WQI value of 849.01. Sharma *et al.*, (2016) assessed water quality index (WQI) of Anasagar Lake at Ajmer and found Lake having low WQI value (49.78) on 100-point scale, corresponding to D category of CPCB. Mukhtar *et al.*, (2017) evaluated water quality of the Brari-Nambal lagoon of Dal Lake, Kashmir using water Quality Index (WQI) and found very poor water quality which falls under grade 'D' with values >75. Rana *et al.*, (2018) assessed the water quality of Himalayan Lake Beni Tal using Water Quality Index (WQI) and found water in good quality on the basis of calculated WQI. Kaur and Ramanathan (2019) investigated the ground water and surface water quality of Kailana Lake, Jodhpur (Rajasthan) and reported ground water quality (deep wells) is not suitable for drinking purpose which may be due to high level of Manganese (0.5 mg/l) and total dissolved solids (500 mg/l) by anthropogenic activities. The quality of lake water showed that the water is within the permissible level except the Pb, value of which exceeds 0.1 mg/l in water which is due to weathering of galena ores in the drainage area. Kumari and Sharma (2019) analyzed the water quality of the Prashar Lake (sacred lake) using water quality index (WQI) and revealed that water quality was degraded in monsoon season due to entering of tourist-generated waste and erosion due to overgrazing on the lake area. Kowalczywska-Madura *et al.*, (2020) assessed the effect of the process of phosphorus (P) loading in waterbodies situated in Western Poland and reported that phosphorus (P) loading in waterbodies is mainly due to release of P from sediments into water column in summer which results in eutrophication of the lakes. Loucif *et al.*, (2020) assessed the physicochemical and microbiological properties of Lake Tonga in northeastern Algeria and reported higher concentration of different groups of faecal bacteria with an average of 32.3×10^3 CFU/100 mL for total heterotrophic bacteria, 24×10^3 CFU/100 mL for total and faecal coliforms and 37×10^3 CFU/100 mL for faecal Streptococci indicating lake in a eutrophic state.

Main Text

Study site: Physiographically the study area is situated at longitude of $74^\circ 33'18''E$ and latitude of $26^\circ 29'14''N$ at an elevation of 530 m above mean sea level and 13 Km to North-West of Ajmer. Topographically, the agro-climatic zone of the Pushkar is categorized as a semiarid ecotone region characterized by more or less plain surface interrupted with low hills, sand dunes and agricultural fields. Agricultural as well as Social, economic and ecological scenario of a region is determined by climate of the region which in turn affected by rainfall, temperature and humidity. It is totally rainfed water body and retains water throughout the year. As the low mountain of Aravali unable to meet the proper rainfall so, on an average there are 26 rainy days in a year. The annual rainfall of Pushkar is approximately 500 to 600 mm as per the meteorological records. With regard to morphometry, dynamics of nutrient and types of inhabiting biota this reservoir resembles a natural pond with total catchment area of 36.71 sq. km.

Figure1: Satellite view of Pushkar Lake

Study of physico-chemical characteristics of water of Pushkar lake was carried out for two years (2019 to 2020) for four different sites. For each station within the lake, sampling will be analyzed thrice on occasion of total 2 festivals in 2019-2020 to obtain concordant values. The festivals chosen on the basis of crowd gathering were Vaishakh Snan and Makar Sankranti. The samples were collected before 15 days, same day and after 15 days of various festivals to be held on Pushkar lake. In the present investigation four

stations were selected so as to characterize the entire pond were 1. Braham Ghat 2. Gau ghat 3. Jaipur ghat 4. Kota ghat.

Figure 2: Location Map of Pushkar (Ajmer District)

Figure 3: Religious activities at Pushkar Sarovar

Methodology The Pond water was analyzed for various physico-chemical parameters. The surface water samples were collected from 10 to 20 cm depth below the surface of the water depending upon the nature of disturbance viz pollution load, pilgrims and human activities, sewage in the lake near shore in 2 litre pre-cleaned polyethylene bottles by grab sampling method for four different sites. After collection bottles were labeled to describe the name of the sampling site, date, time and conditions during the sampling. Seasonal monitoring of pond water is carried out through comprehensive analysis of physico-chemical parameters encompassing estimation of general parameters like pH, TDS, DO, BOD, turbidity, temperature. Some in situ parameters like pH, TDS, dissolved oxygen, etc. will be measured immediately in the field after sampling and for other parameters, the water sample was refrigerated at 4⁰C, to be analyze them later. During the research all the analysis were carried out by following standard procedures mentioned in standard Methods for the Examination of water and waste water” 21th edition (APHA, 2005), published by “American Public Health association, American Water works Association and Water Environment Federation”, “Biological and Chemical Methods for Water Pollution Studies” (Trivedi and Goel 1986).

Result and Discussion The results obtained by physicochemical analysis of all samples are given in Table 1. Differences in various parameters were observed during different festival times from different ghats of Pushkar lake in 2019-2020. The data for different physico-chemical parameters of water were recorded in Table-1 to assess the water quality status of Pushkar Lake during the Makar Sankranti and Vaishakh Snan festivals

Temperature: Temperature has a considerable impact on water chemistry, and when the temperature and chemical composition of a lake's water exceed particular thresholds, a variety of events can occur. During the investigation, the temperature

varied from 16.3°C to 17.6° C during Makar Sankranti festival. This may be due to low environmental conditions of January month. The highest temperature value was recorded during Vaishakh Snan was 24° C in May month. The mean of temperature observed in 2019's study was 22.2 °C with corresponding WQI value 9.32 of while in 2020's study was 22.3 °C with corresponding WQI value of 9.26. The clear difference is seen that during COVID's restriction does not impact on water temperature it may affect by atmospheric temperature.

Figure No. 4 Graphical representation of variations in Temperature of various study sites.

pH: pH is a measurement of the amount of H⁺ ions in water. It can be any number from 0 to 14. pH values fluctuate mostly as a result of component input into water bodies. The majority of biological processes and biochemical reactions are regulated by pH. The pH of the Pushkar lake water was found to be slightly neutral in the current study, ranging from 6.8 to 7.3 and being nearly constant on each occasion. The pH of a typical eutrophic lake, according to Spence (1967), ranges from 7.6 to 9.7. The current findings support Spence's (1967) statement that the Pushkar lake is eutrophic based on its pH range. During the Makar Sankranti festival in 2019, the average pH was highest in Brahma Ghat and Gau Ghat (7.3) with corresponding WQI value of 10.27, while it was highest (7.2) with corresponding WQI value of 10.08 whereas it was 6.9 in the 2020 study with corresponding WQI value of 9.33. at Jaipur ghat during Vaishakh Snan Because of the COVID19 pandemic's lockdown restrictions, it was almost the same during rest event's time due to decreased pollution and little anthropogenic activities.

Figure No. 5 Graphical representation of variations in pH of various study sites.

Total dissolved solids: The term solid refers to the matter that remains as residue upon evaporation. Total solids include both dissolved solids and suspended solids. A large number of salts are found dissolved in water. A high concentration of dissolved solids raises the density of water, affects freshwater organisms' osmoregulation, reduces the solubility of gases (such as O₂), diminishes the usefulness of water for drinking, and leads to eutrophication of the aquatic ecosystem. In 2019 the average TDS was observed highest (583.2 mg/L) at Jaipur ghat during Makar Sankranti. In 2020 it was also highest at Jaipur ghat during Makar Sankranti festival. The mean of TDS observed in 2019's study was 575.5 mg/L with corresponding WQI value of 1.40. During rest events it was decreased gradually due to less pollution and negligible anthropogenic activities due to lockdown's restrictions of COVID-19 pandemic.

Figure No. 6 Graphical representation of variations in TDS of various study sites.

Dissolved oxygen: All aquatic species rely on dissolved oxygen in water, and it is thought to be the factor that represents the physical and biological processes occurring in a water body. It is necessary for the development and maintenance of life. It has a significant impact on the nature of an entire aquatic environment. The oxygen that a water body obtains comes mostly from two sources: the atmosphere and the photosynthetic activity of chlorophyll-bearing plants. The concentration of dissolved oxygen is also affected by surface agitation caused by temperature, the rate of respiration of living organisms, and the rate of decomposition of dead organic matter. In 2019 the average Dissolved Oxygen was observed highest during Makar Sankranti festival at Gau ghat and Jaipur ghat. In 2020 it was highest at Jaipur Ghat and Kota Ghat during Vaishakh Snan. During rest events it was increased gradually due to less pollution and negligible anthropogenic activities due to lockdown's restrictions of

COVID-19 pandemic. The mean of Dissolved Oxygen observed in 2019's study was 5.2 mg/L with WQI of 10.67 while in 2020's study was 6.2 mg/L. with WQI of 13.73.

Figure No. 7 Graphical representation of variations in Dissolved oxygen of various study sites.

Table-1: Mean of all parameters studied during the Makar Sankranti and Vaishakh Snan festivals at Pushkar Lake during both years' studies at different Ghats.

Parameters	Year of study	Makar Sankranti Festival				Vaishakh Snan			
		Brahma Ghat	Gau ghat	Jaipur ghat	Kota ghat	Brahma Ghat	Gau ghat	Jaipur ghat	Kota ghat
pH	2019	7.3	7.3	7.1	7.2	7.1	7.1	7.2	7.1
	2020	7.1	7.1	7.2	7.0	6.8	6.8	6.9	6.8
Phosphate	2019	0.5	0.5	0.6	0.4	0.6	0.6	0.6	0.5
	2020	0.5	0.5	0.6	0.4	0.4	0.3	0.4	0.3
Nitrogen-Nitrate	2019	5.8	5.8	5.9	5.5	6.2	6.1	6.1	6.0
	2020	5.6	5.6	5.8	5.5	4.9	4.8	4.9	5.0
TDS	2019	571.1	550.5	583.2	355.6	564.6	581.6	567.9	483.9
	2020	568.5	542.8	575.5	444.9	309.5	320.3	314.9	313.6
Dissolved O ₂	2019	5.0	5.4	5.4	5.3	5.2	5.1	5.2	5.2
	2020	4.9	5.2	5.5	5.1	5.7	5.8	5.8	5.9
Temperature	2019	17.2	16.8	16.3	16.3	23.9	24.0	23.9	23.2
	2020	17.6	17.0	16.6	17.2	23.3	23.5	23.8	23.8
BOD	2019	14.8	14.6	15.0	14.8	14.7	15.4	15.2	15.6
	2020	14.7	14.6	14.9	14.6	14.4	14.4	14.7	14.5
Turbidity	2019	73.4	74.8	80.9	75.2	84.4	84.8	84.8	79.1
	2020	74.6	80.5	79.7	73.7	57.7	56.3	56.7	57.7

Biochemical Oxygen demand: The aerobic decomposition of organic matter by microbes primarily depends upon the availability of dissolved oxygen. The rate of removal or consumption of oxygen by microorganisms, for this degradation is called the BOD or biological oxygen demand of the water body. During the Makar Sankranti festival, the value of biochemical oxygen demand ranged from 14.6 to 15.0 mg/L, with corresponding WQI value of 2.33 to 2.23 while during Vaishakh Snan occasions, it ranged from 14.7 to 15.6 mg/L with corresponding WQI value of 2.30 to 2.10. The mean of BOD observed in 2019's study was 15.1mg/L with corresponding WQI value of 2.21, while in 2020's study was 13.9mg/L with corresponding WQI value of 2.50. The variations could be caused by an excess of organic materials introduced by human activities such as gifting flowers, garlands, and other religious items, providing food for fish, birds, and other animals and mass bathing.

Figure No. 8 Graphical representation of variations in BOD of various study sites.

Nitrogen-Nitrate: Nitrate is the highest oxidized form of nitrogen, and in water its most important source is biological oxidation of nitrogenous organic matter. It is an integral component of all essential organic molecules, without whom the existence of life cannot be expected. In 2019 the average Nitrogen- Nitrate was observed highest (6.2 mg/L) at Brahma ghat during Vaishakh Snan. In 2020 it was also highest (5.9 mg/L) at Jaipur ghat during Makar Sankranti festival. The mean of Nitrogen- Nitrate observed in 2019’s study was 5.9 mg/L with corresponding WQI value of 6.38, while in 2020’s study was 4.3mg/L with corresponding WQI value of 7.03. During rest events it was decreased gradually due to less pollution and negligible anthropogenic activities due to lockdown’s restrictions of COVID-19 pandemic.

Figure No. 9 Graphical representation of variations in Nitrogen-Nitrate of various study sites.

Turbidity: The clarity of water is measured by turbidity. Turbidity increases as the amount of suspended (organic or mineral) solids increases. In this study the variations in turbidity were measured during the 4 major events of Pushkar Lake. The same parameter is observed on same days in the year of 2019 and 2020. The turbidity level was fluctuated in the study of 2019 during event times due to presence of various pollutant or anthropogenic activities. In 2019 the average turbidity was observed highest during Vaishakh Snan at Jaipur and Kota ghat. In 2020 it was highest at Gau ghat during Makar Sankranti festival. The mean of turbidity observed in 2019’s study was 78.2 NTU with corresponding WQI value of 2.06 while, in 2020’s study was 47.8 NTU with corresponding WQI value of 3.17. During rest events it was decreased

gradually due to less pollution and negligible anthropogenic activities due to lockdown's restrictions of COVID-19 pandemic.

Figure No. 10 Graphical representation of variations in Turbidity of various study sites.

Phosphate: In aquatic systems, phosphorus can be found as free ions, absorbed into sediments and soils, or mineralized in soil, rocks, and sediments. In this study the Phosphate level was fluctuated in the study of 2019 during event times due to presence of various pollutant or anthropogenic activities. In 2019 the average Phosphate was observed highest at almost all Ghats on all occasions simultaneously. In 2020 it was also highest at Jaipur ghat during Makar Sankranti festival. The mean of Phosphate observed in 2019's study was 0.5mg/L with corresponding WQI value of 5.28 while in 2020's study was 0.4mg/L with corresponding WQI value of 5.66. During rest events it was decreased gradually due to less pollution and negligible anthropogenic activities due to lockdown's restrictions of COVID-19 pandemic.

Figure No. 11 Graphical representation of variations in Phosphate of various study sites

Conclusion The overall situation revealed that the total dissolved solids, BOD, Phosphates, Nitrates and turbidity etc. show considerable increase and remarkable decrease in pH and DO during the investigation period. In short, the water quality of the lake under study is degraded considerably due to contamination of water by sewage from the diverse anthropogenic activities. In fact, the pollution levels are much higher at festival times, particularly on Makar-Sankranti time due to the Hindu community's excess religious activities on that day. These lower water quality index values were due to influx of pollutants directly into the water body through anthropogenic activities, while the WQI value were found comparatively high during 2019, where anthropogenic activities were less pronounced due to lockdown's restrictions of COVID-19 pandemic. Observed value of water quality index clearly reflected that Water Quality of lake was "average" and belongs to "C" category of CPCB on 100-point scale. Water quality from studied Lake is unsafe for consumption of human use and therefore need serious attention. Source identification should be undertaken using modern tools such as remote sensing to locate and isolate the flourishing source. To cope up with the problem of eutrophication in the lake system, besides source control, immediate alleviating actions should be taken. Water quality monitoring as a regular monitoring program should be commenced so as to keep a continuous check on the quality of water. Cleaning the lake by removal of accumulations of silts and sediments in order to restore the lake capacity that is DESILTING and by enlarging the channel through deepening and widening that is DREDGING. Canalization of streams that carry run-off is required for lake restoration so that the inflow is diverted towards the lake. A distinct place in the Ghat must be year marked for ashes and dead bones immersion, and the number of ashes should be kept to a minimum (10-45 grammes).

References

1. Manderia, S., Reshi, J.M. and Manderia, K. (2014). To evaluate the water quality status and responsible factors for variation in Anchar Lake, Kashmir. *IOSR- Journal of Environmental Science, Toxicology and Food Technology*, 8 (2-IV), 55-62.
2. Shekar, G., Narayan, L. and Muniyellappa, R. M. (2015). Impact of urbanization and study of water quality index on Gidadakonenahalli Lake, Bangalore urban district, Karnataka, India. *Advances in Forestry Science*, 2(1), 7-12.
3. Sharma, P.C., Ranga, M.M. and Mishra, D. (2016). Effect of mass bathing on water quality of sacred lakes of Rajasthan, India. *Pollution Research*, 35 (1), 67-71.
4. Mukhtar, F., Chisti, H. and Bhat, S. A. (2017). Comparative Characterization of Water Quality of Brari-Nambal La goon of Dal Lake Before and After Kashmir Floods. *Current Environmental Engineering*, 4(2), 121-129.
5. Rana, K. S., Sharma, R. C., Tiwari, V. and Kumar, R. (2018). assessment of surface water quality of the Himalayan Lake benital India. *Current Research in Hydrology and Water Resources*.
6. Kaur, L. and Ramanathan, A. L. (2019). Assessment of Major Ion Chemistry in Ground Water and Surface Water of Kailana Lake Area of Jodhpur (Rajasthan). *Journal of Water Resource Engineering and Management*, 3(2), 42-56.
7. Kumari, R. and Sharma, R. C. (2019). Assessment of water quality index and multivariate analysis of high-altitude sacred Lake Prashar, Himachal Pradesh,

- India. *International Journal of Environmental Science and Technology*, 16(10), 6125-6134.
8. Loucif, K., Neffar, S., Menasria, T., Maazi, M. C., Houhamdi, M. and Chenchouni, H. (2020). *Physico-chemical and bacteriological quality assessment of surface water at Lake Tonga in Algeria. Environmental Nanotechnology, Monitoring and Management*, 13, 100284.
 9. APHA AWWA, W. P. C. F. (1998). *Standard methods for the examination of water and wastewater 20th edition. American Public Health Association, American Water Work Association, Water Environment Federation, Washington, DC.*
 10. Bhatt, L. R., Lacoul, P., Lekhak, H. D., & Jha, P. K. (1999). *Physico-chemical characteristics and phytoplanktons of Taudaha lake, Kathmandu. Pollution Research*, 18(4), 353-358.
 11. Spence, D.H.N. (1967). *Factors controlling the distribution of freshwater macrophytes with particular reference to the lochs of Scotland. J. Ecol.* 55, 147–170.
 12. Shiklomanov, I. A. (1993). *World freshwater resources. Water in crisis: a guide to the world's freshwater resources. Clim. Change*, 45, 379-382.
 13. Spence, D. H. N. (1982). *The zonation of plants in freshwater lakes. In Advances in ecological research (Vol. 12, pp. 37-125). Academic Press.*
 14. Wetzel, G.W. (2001). *Limnology: Lake and River Ecosystems. Academic Press, New York. Pp. 15-42.*
 15. Prati, L. et al. (1971). *Assessment of Surface Water Quality by a single Index of Pollution. Water Research*, 5 (9), 741-751.
 16. Brown, R.M., McClelland, N.I., Deininger, R.A. and Tozer, R.G. (1970). "Water quality index-do we dare? *Water Sewage Works*, 117(10), 339-343.